

Synthesis of Peptides of β -Amino-acids. Part III

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Synthesis of some new peptides of β -amino-acids from activated esters of *N*-benzylidene- β -amino-acids are described.

Wieland *et al.*¹ prepared Schiff bases of α -amino-acids by condensing aromatic aldehyde with potassium salt of α -amino-acids, but that these bases were found not useful for peptide synthesis. *N*-Benzylidene derivatives have again been revived for an alternating group for lysine. Sheehan² prepared the yellow Schiff bases from 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde for the synthesis of peptides. There is an increase in stability of the ring due to hydrogen bonding.

The present work was therefore undertaken to ascertain the usefulness of different substituted aromatic aldehydes for the protection of the amino group of β -amino-acids and the Schiff bases, thus prepared, were then employed for the synthesis of peptides of β -amino-acids. The β -amino-acids were condensed with benzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, and the anisaldehyde in 0.1*N* potassium hydroxide at the room temperature. The Schiff bases, thus obtained, were then refluxed with ethyl chloroacetate to furnish the activated esters of the protected β -amino-acids. These activated esters on condensation with the appropriate β -amino-acid esters yielded peptides of β -amino-acids.

1. *Annalen*, 1952, 588, 15.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 84, 2417.

In all, eighteen peptides have been prepared from three β -amino-acids, viz., β -alanine, β -aminobutyric acid, and β -amino- β -phenylpropionic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl esters of β -amino-acids were prepared by following the method of Boissonas³. Thionyl chloride (0.1M) was added (10°) to anhydrous ethanol (50 ml); the β -amino-acid (0.1M) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The ester was obtained by passing a slow stream of ammonia into a suspension of the ester hydrochloride in chloroform.

N-Benzylidene- β -amino-acids.—The potassium salt of the required β -amino-acid (0.1M), aromatic aldehyde (0.1M), and *N*/10-KOH (20 ml) were mixed and the solution was stirred for 3 hr. It was left overnight at the room temperature, when the Schiff base separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The m.p., yields, and analyses of the Schiff bases are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

$$\text{R}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\overset{\text{R}'}{\underset{|}{\text{C}}}\text{H}-\text{CH}_2-\text{COOK}$$

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Fouud.	Read.
1	Ph	H	*280°	82	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NK	6.41	6.60
2	..	Me	*248°	79	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ NK	6.00	6.10
3	..	Ph	*238°	81	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ NK	4.53	4.89
4	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	H	248°	74	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₄ N ₂ K	10.58	10.70
5	..	Me	239°	68	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ K	10.03	10.20
6	..	Ph	250°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ K	8.00	8.30
7	<i>p</i> -OMe.C ₆ H ₄	H	*246°	59	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ NK	5.40	5.60
8	..	Me	*251°	81	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ NK	5.18	5.40
9	..	Ph	*240°	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ NK	4.02	4.30

*Melts with decomposition.

Ethoxycarbonylmethyl-N-benzylidene- β -amino-acids.—Potassium salt of the protected β -amino-acid (0.05M), ethyl chloroacetate (0.1M), triethylamine (0.05M), and dry ethyl acetate (60 ml) were refluxed on a water bath. The refluxing was continued until separation of KCl was complete. The potassium chloride was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated when the activated ester separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from benzene. The m.p., yields, analyses of these activated esters are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Sl. No.	M.P.	%Yield.	M.P.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1	200°	56	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	5.08	5.30
2	184°	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	4.88	5.05
3	165°	61	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₄ N	4.01	4.12
4	189°	48	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂	8.88	9.09
4	175°	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₂	8.54	8.70
6	206°	65	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂	7.01	7.20
7	210°	41	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₅ N	4.82	5.00
8	185°	50	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	4.41	4.60
9	164°	49	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N	3.32	3.60

N. B. R and R' are the same as in Table I.

N-Protected β -Amino-acid Peptides

N-Protected activated ester (0.004M), β -amino-acid ester (0.004M), and dry benzene (10 ml) were refluxed on a water bath for 3 hr. The peptide crystallised on cooling the reaction mixture. It was filtered and recrystallised from benzene. The m.p., yields, analyses, and R_f values of these peptides are recorded in Table III. The chromatogram was run in butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5).

TABLE III

R'	R''	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	R_f .	Found.	Reqd.
A. R = Ph.							
H	H	110°	60	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₂	0.34	C : 65.01 H : 7.04 N : 9.80	65.20 7.20 10.10
H	Me	100°	71	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂	0.28	C : 65.90 H : 7.38 N : 9.41	65.20 7.60 9.60
Me	H	75°	64	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂	0.43	C : 66.00 H : 7.41 N : 9.39	66.20 7.60 9.60
Me	Me	68°	81	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	0.68	C : 66.80 H : 7.50 N : 8.48	67.10 7.80 8.70
Ph	H	87	86	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	0.63	C : 71.40 H : 6.60 N : 7.83	71.50 6.80 8.09
Ph	Me	94°	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	0.53	C : 72.00 H : 7.00 N : 7.60	72.10 7.10 7.70

TABLE III (contd.)

R'	R''	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	R _f .	Found.	Reqd.
B. R = NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .							
H	H	45°	54	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃	0.63	C : 55.84 H : 5.72 N : 13.61	56.00 5.90 13.80
H	Me	96°	59	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	0.43	C : 57.00 H : 5.74 N : 12.38	57.30 6.00 12.50
Me	H	103°	61	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₃	0.58	C : 57.10 H : 5.95 N : 12.34	57.30 6.00 12.50
Me	Me	111°	68	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	0.49	C : 58.20 H : 6.31 N : 12.00	58.40 6.50 12.03
Ph	H	120°	84	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₃	0.39	N : 10.32	10.50
Ph	Me	132°	72	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₅ N ₃	0.28	N : 10.10	10.20
C. R = OEt.C ₆ H ₄ .							
H	H	141°	68	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂	0.41	C : 62.30 H : 6.10 N : 9.11	62.70 7.10 9.30
H	Me	161°	65	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	0.36	C : 63.20 H : 7.15 N : 8.48	63.70 7.50 8.70
Me	H	151°	48	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	0.42	N : 8.46	8.70
Me	Me	139°	52	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂	0.51	N : 8.12	8.30
Ph	H	122°	61	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₂	0.54	N : 7.24	7.30
Ph	Me	134°	74	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₂	0.49	N : 7.01	7.07

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